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Executive Summary

In Task 13.1 a basic e-learning course on Oncogenomics addressing physicians and other health professionals was developed and disseminated in Europe to foster implementation of Personalised Cancer Medicine. The Learning Objectives (LOs) of the course aimed at improving knowledge and know-how of non-geneticist health professionals on basic principles of genetics and main applications of genomics in cancer prevention, diagnosis and care. The LOs were identified in the iPAAC Joint Action (Grant Agreement number: 801520 — iPAAC — HP-JA-2017), in which a pilot English version of the e-learning was tested in Italy.

Building on the results of this preliminary pilot, in Can.Heal (Task 13.1) the training materials were reviewed and translated into four latin languages (IT,SP,FR,PT). The teaching modality was inspired by the Problem Based Learning approach used in adult learning settings to promote active participation. Self-assessment tests, certification test and a satisfaction questionnaire were integrated in the course to evaluate its efficacy in different perspectives. The English version of the Can.Heal e-learning course on Oncogenomics was accredited by UEMS-EACCME, a reference European provider of Continuing Medical Education (CME) credits. Versions in other languages were accredited by national deputed authorities for CME certification (IT, SP).

The English and Italian versions of the course were both deployed on the e-learning platform of the Italian National Institute of Health (Istituto Superiore di Sanità-ISS) which, while primarily devoted to CME training activities of the National Health Service workforce (www.eduiss.it), includes as well a section for courses addressing an international audience. The Spanish version of the course was made available on the e-oncologia training platform (<https://e-oncologia.org>) of the Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO).

The e-learning module was developed in the Totara Learn 11 learning management system. This allowed to export the learning material under a Moodle format, facilitating its adaptation to other country-specific platforms (SP, FR). The dissemination of the course is currently ongoing. Data collected during deployment in different countries will allow to assess the impact of the course in terms of adhesion, knowledge increase and users' satisfaction.

The main factors facilitating the users' adhesion were the accreditation of the course, the cost-free access, the use of native language. The implementation on running national platforms for training the health workforce, the distance learning modality, the technological solutions used to develop the course and the availability of performance indicators are factors that facilitate the adoption of this educational intervention. The main challenges to be considered include intellectual property rights, implementation requirements and regular update of the scientific content.

1. Introduction and objective of the deliverable

This report describes the activity performed in Task 13.1 to develop and disseminate to European health professionals a distance learning course on the basic principles of genetics and the current applications of genomics in oncology.

Cancer diagnosis and treatment are becoming increasingly molecular-based, thanks to the decreasing costs of sequencing technologies and increasing knowledge of the human genome. The widespread use of NGS techniques offers increased opportunities to tailor cancer prevention and treatment, through targeted agents and immunotherapies.

This requires updating regularly the genetic and genomic literacy of healthcare providers, who are at the interface between the patients and the oncologists. Gaps in the genetic and genomic education of health care providers have long been appreciated as a roadblock to the implementation of research discoveries into clinical practice. In a rapidly evolving scenario, the development (and maintenance) of a competent workforce has become a prerequisite for bridging the research and clinical settings.

The Can.Heal course “*Oncogenomics for Health Professionals* “ is addressed to physicians of all specialties as well as general practitioners, biologists and pharmacists, with the general scope of improving their knowledge and know-how on the basic principles of genetics and on the major clinical applications of genomic technologies in cancer prevention, diagnosis and treatment.

The training material was developed in English and subsequently translated in Italian, Spanish, French and Portuguese to disseminate the course in different pilot countries joining the Can.Heal Consortium.

We herein describe the stepwise strategy employed to design the course. We document the activities carried out to develop, translate, and get accreditation of the course material at national and at European levels, and to deliver the course online on national platforms for Continuing Medical Education in Italy and other countries.

We furthermore elaborate on the lessons learnt from our experience to identify key elements facilitating the adherence of health professionals and the adoption of such educational initiatives by relevant institutions.

2. Work performed

2.1 Course design

2.1.1 Learning Objectives

The course is structured in four *Learning Objectives* (LOs). The content of the LOs was built based on 37 core competencies in cancer genomics required for non-geneticist physicians, which were identified in the iPAAC Joint Action (Grant Agreement number: 801520 — iPAAC — HP-JA-2017), (Innovative Partnership for Action Against Cancer) as an objective of WP6 on cancer genomics (www.ipaac.eu). The list of core competencies was set up via a two-step consensus-based approach, *i.e.*, first identification of the items via systematic literature review and then refinement of the identified items by an international expert panel, based on a modified Delphi method¹.

The original set of core competencies identified in iPAAC belong to the *Knowledge, Attitudes* and *Abilities* domains. Because of the online training modality inherent to the e-learning course, we retained all the competencies related to the *Knowledge* domain and a few competencies from the *Attitudes* domain, which can be easily transferred and measured in a low interaction e-learning setting. However, competencies related to the *Abilities* domain could not be included, as they require an interactive setting.

The four LOs cover multiple topics ranging from the genetic basis of cancer to genetic testing, OMICS technologies, pharmacogenomics, and personalized medicine. A description of the contents of the LOs and the corresponding core competencies used to define them are reported in **Table 1**.

- LO1 aims at recapitulating the **basic principles of human genetics**, elucidating how gene variation may contribute to cancer and clarifying the difference between inherited and acquired sequence changes. Upon completion of LO1, the participants are expected to understand why cancer is a genetic disease and which OMICS technologies are most relevant for the identification of the molecular signature of cancer.
- The primary aims of LO2 are to describe the **genetic heterogeneity underlying cancer susceptibility** and the difference between the most common **genetic and genomic tests**, both conventional and NGS-based, used in clinical oncology (e.g., somatic vs. constitutional testing). Emphasis is placed on understanding who should be tested for cancer predisposition and on the significance and interpretation of key terms and concepts such as variant of uncertain significance, incidental findings, and polygenic risk score.
- LO3 explores the multifaceted aspects of **genetic counselling** when cancer predisposition is suspected to segregate within a family. The specific markers of hereditary cancer syndromes and the criteria and categories for genetic testing are listed with explanatory examples. Management strategies for individuals at high genetic risk of cancer are also covered.
- LO4 aims at addressing why treatment is not successful in all patients and why some individuals are more prone than others to adverse effects. To this end, the concepts of **biomarkers, pharmacogenetics, pharmacogenomics**, drug repositioning, and personalized medicine in oncology are extensively discussed. A relatively small number of items belonging to the *Knowledge* domain are used to build this last LO, as all the background information needed to comprehend its content is provided in the previous LOs.

2.1.2 Learning methodology

The course was developed according to the main models of andragogic training, specifically to the **Problem-based Learning (PBL) method** – a training methodology that encourages the participants to “learn to learn” by solving real-world problems that reflect their professional field.^{2,3}

In the PBL method, the starting point of the training process is the Problem, which prompts the participants to reflect on their professional experience and knowledge and to identify their learning needs relevant to the course learning objectives. The questions and keywords in the Problem guide the learning process towards practical implications in the participants’ professional field. The participants are thus actively involved and encouraged to expand their knowledge and to acquire new Problem-solving skills, studying the training material selected by the experts and carrying out additional, independent research.

The Learning Management System (LSM) used to develop the e-learning is the Totara Learn 11, which is based on a Moodle extension and offers all technical resources to implement the PBL methodology. Low Interaction, asynchronous mode, and no facilitation are the main technical features chosen.

The PBL methodology is set up using platform tools such as feedback, web pages, quizzes and other learning tools (e.g., the Shareable Content Object Reference Model, SCORM). The e-learning path is scheduled in sequential steps, where access to the activities in each unit is allowed only when those of the previous one are completed.

The **PBL** cycle opens on the introduction of the central challenge or problem (Problem presentation). Participants then engage in a critical analysis activity, often utilizing a SCORM-based tool, to dissect the problem and define specific learning objectives (LO identification). This is followed by an independent exploration phase, where participants have access to a range of resources: bibliographic references, curated website lists, in-depth reading materials, and expert video tutorials (Exploration phase). Finally, participants apply their acquired knowledge and skills to come up with a solution to the original problem (Problem solution).

2.1.3 Evaluation tools

The e-learning course includes the three following assessment tools:

- *Self-assessment test.* This mandatory test includes 12 Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs), three for each LO, offered both at the entry (T0, pre-test) and at the end of the course (T1, post-test). This test allows the participants to assess their own level of knowledge. For each question, there are four possible answers out of which only one is correct. A minimal score is not required. At T1, participants receive feedback on their wrong answers, pointing to the specific LO to be reviewed before taking the final certification test.
- *Final certification test.* This mandatory test is taken at the end of the course, enabling the participants to earn CME credits. A minimum of 75% correct answers are required to pass it. Three hours and a maximum of three attempts are allowed to complete the test, which include 60 MCQs, 15 for each LO.
- *Satisfaction questionnaire.* This mandatory survey is taken at the very end of the course to participants who completed the *final certification test*. It allows participants to evaluate different aspects of the e-learning process, through 18 closed Likert-type questions, including seven about the perceived quality of the methodology, eight about the educational contents of the course, and three about the operability of the platform. In addition, two open questions allow to evaluate the strengths of the course and ask for suggestions to improve it.

2.2 Development of the training material

The training materials used in the Exploration phase of the PBL-cycle were developed by three Italian professors in medical genetics. Prof. Paola Ghiorzo (University of Genua) developed the material pertaining to LO1, Prof. Maurizio Genuardi (Catholic University of Rome) was responsible for LO2 and LO3, Prof Emilio Di Maria (University of Genua) prepared the material of LO4.

The activity in Can.Heal leveraged the work done in the iPAAC JA in which the e-learning on Oncogenomics for Health Professionals was first tested in Italy.⁴ Overall 365 Italian health professionals (60% physicians and 40% biologists) completed the course and their feedback provided insights for improving the implementation phase performed in Can.Heal.

The main modification regarded the module on pharmacogenomics (LO4) which has been developed de-novo. The materials of the other three LOs were revised to improve the clarity of some questions in the self-assessment and in the certification test, and to update the references in the supporting and reading materials, and in the video tutorials.

The Problem presentation and solution were developed by the course's scientific secretariat at ISS with the collaboration of experts from the Consortium (Dr. Arcangela De Nicolo). The self-assessment and certification questionnaires were developed by the teachers in charge of each LO. The satisfaction questionnaire was developed by the ISS Training Service.

All single items developed in the e-learning "Oncogenomics for Health Professionals" and their location in the PBL cycle are described in **Table 2**.

The English version of the Training material was released by the teachers in February 2023.

2.3 Expert revision of the English training material

To further improve the e-learning course based on the pilot participants' feedback, we initiated a revision of the course material prior to its wider release. An international committee of three experts appointed from the Can.Heal Consortium first revised individually the material of each LO and subsequently had joint meetings to reach consensus on the relevant revisions to be proposed to the responsible teacher. Main issues regarded the harmonisation of the terminology used, unclear statements, and relevant references to be added or revised. The authors approved most of the comments of the independent reviewers. This independent expert revision contributed to improve the quality and clarity of the training materials. The revision was beneficial for the course's translation and for its dissemination in Europe as a tool for progressing on personalised cancer prevention and care. The revisions took place sequentially for each LO and were finalized between May-October 2023. The latest course's module to be finalised was the one related to LO4 which was the only being developed de-novo.

2.4 Translations of the English training material

A main barrier reported in the satisfaction survey by Italian professionals⁴ participating in the pilot phase was the use of the English language. Health professionals using Latin based languages, especially in countries with a large population like Italy, France and Spain, are not always familiar with training material in English. According to the survey, Preference for learning in one's native language was more prevalent in the older age groups and was progressively less relevant for younger audiences. In the implementation of the Can.Heal course we planned to address this barrier by translating all the course material in Italian, Spanish, French and Portuguese, through a two steps process:

- i) Automated translation via AI assisted software (Deep-L)
- ii) Expert revision of the automated translations

The quality of the automated translations was proven to be high and valid in 90-95% of cases. However, an expert revision was necessary due to the highly specific terminology of the scientific content. For this purpose, scientific domains experts in the respective native language were appointed in each of the four pilot countries involved in Task 13.1 (ISS-Italy, ICO-Spain, IC-France, INSA-Portugal). This work allowed to identify small issues or typos and further contributed to improve the quality and readability of the proposed training materials in four Latin-based language.

The video tutorials with professors voice-over had to be translated as well. Italian and English voice recordings were released by the three appointed professors. Voice recording in the other languages were re-recorded separately in each participating country. Translation and calibration in Spain has been carried out by the team of the Thoracic Tumors Unit at the Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO).

2.5 CME accreditation

Continuing Medical Education (CME) is becoming increasingly mandatory in Europe. To improve dissemination and encourage participation of health professionals, we planned to obtain CME accreditation of the e-learning on Oncogenomics developed in the frame of Can.Heal. We did it both at European level (for the English version) and at national level (for the translated versions).

At the European level, we identified the **European Accreditation Council for Continuing Medical Education (EACCME®)** established by the **Union Européenne des Médecins Spécialistes (UEMS)** with the aim of encouraging the highest standards in the development, delivery and harmonisation of continuing medical education.

The UEMS was founded in 1958 with the aim of representing the interests of specialist doctors at an international level. The UEMS is a non-governmental voluntary organisation whose members are the national medical organisations that represent medical specialists in the European Union and in associated countries.

The purpose of the EACCME® was to provide accreditation of international CME in Europe and to facilitate the recognition of credits between the various countries in Europe. In order to reach this goal, the UEMS-EACCME® signed agreements of cooperation with the majority of countries in Europe, and also outside of Europe (the full list of countries is available at www.eaccme.eu).

In order to support this recognition process, the UEMS-EACCME® introduced a common “CME currency”: the European CME Credit (ECMEC®).

The countries with which the EACCME® has signed agreements recognise EACCME® credits. All the other countries may recognise EACCME® credits on a voluntary basis.

The accreditation process in UEMS-EACCME was particularly complex. Specific adaptations were needed due to the set of rules and training categories envisaged. The application process started in November 2023 and required multiple exchanges to identify the proper application framework for the Can.Heal course. As a result, we were invited to extend the number of certificative questions (from 48 to 60) to fulfill the EACCME criteria. After successfully applying for accreditation, three independent reviewers appointed by EACCME revised the English version of the e-learning course on the EDUISS online platform. The Can.Heal course was accredited in the EACCME system in April 2024. In total 12 hours credits were recognised to the Can.Heal e-learning on Oncogenomics, 3 hours for each LO module.

Accreditation at national level was obtained in Italy and Spain, with the corresponding national authorities appointed for the CME certification of training programmes.

In Italy the AGENAS body (<https://ecm.agenas.it/>) accredited the Italian version of the Can.Heal course for 16 hours credits.

In Spain the course was accredited for 16 hours, and 2,3 CME credits by Consejo Catalán de Formación Continuada de las Profesiones Sanitarias – Comisión de Formación Continuada del Sistema Nacional de Salud.

2.6 Setup of the e-learning training platform(s)

The ISS Training Service, in collaboration with the ISS scientific secretariat of the course, was responsible for delivering the Can.Heal Oncogenomics course on the ISS national

distance training platform (EDUISS). The EDUISS platform is widely used by Italian Health Professionals, particularly since the Covid pandemic, which induced a worldwide change in the training habits, with onsite courses being easily and frequently proposed online or hybrid. The **Totara Learn 11** was used as Learning Management System (LSM) to develop the e-learning on the EDUISS platform. Totara Learn 11 is based on a **Moodle** extension and offers all technical resources to implement the Problem Based Learning methodology. Specifically, we used platform tools such as feedback, web pages, quizzes and other learning tools (e.g., the Shareable Content Object Reference Model, SCORM). The e-learning path was scheduled in sequential steps, whereby access to the activities in each unit was allowed only after completing those of the previous one.

Both the English and the Italian versions of the Can.Heal e-learning course were developed on the EDUISS platform. The first one was intended to serve professionals in countries of the Consortium where health professionals are familiar with English training materials, e.g. Greece, Slovenia, Lithuania, Malta etc... The second one has been implemented for Italian professionals only.

The English version of the training platform was exported in Moodle to serve as a basis for building up native language training platforms of the Can.Heal course in countries other than Italy (Spain, France, Portugal).

ISS shared the English Moodle platform with the WP13 partners involved.

The four Tutorials and the Problem solutions were directly processed using the final translated files (.pptx). The Articulate Storyline software was used to import them and add the audio tracks in native language.

The Problem-Exercise, the starting point of the PBL cycle, was a more complex object and the source file (.story) was shared with the partners to facilitate adaptations to local language.

All country-specific versions of the Can.Heal course had to follow the **same methodology** and thus comply with the following guidelines:

- be faithfully translated
- preserve the original architecture and layout of the file (.story) in accordance with the PBL teaching methodology (each unit can only be accessed upon completion of the previous one)

Special attention was paid to possible **legal issues**, in particular to provide transparent information on how the e-learning module was developed.

Of course, the authors could not be asked to review and approve the translation of their lessons. They only checked and approved the English and Italian versions.

Therefore, to avoid any possible controversy, we had to clearly state how the translated materials were produced. A specific disclaimer was added for this purpose:

- on the cover slide of each Tutorial stating that "The original tutorial by Prof XY was written in English. The translation of the French/Spanish/etc texts of the tutorial was edited and validated by Prof/Dr WZ".
- on the first page of the Problem Solution, to state that "The original problem solution was written in English. The translation of the French/Spanish/etc texts of the Problem Solution was edited and validated by ZZ".

Another legal issue concerned the ISS intellectual property rights, with the need that the Tutorials and the Problem Solution retain the original layouts and the ISS logo.

A **letter of intent** was agreed and signed by the parties (ISS and WP13 partners developing the e-learning on their national platforms for CME). The aim of the letter was to ensure a common understanding on the respect of the above-cited conditions (disclaimers on translations, original layout, and respect of the original settings to ensure faithful application of the PBL didactic method).

3. Main achievements

3.1 Training materials

All the training materials and evaluation questionnaires developed in the Can.Heal e-learning course on “*Oncogenomics for health professionals*” are listed in **Table 2**.

In brief the Can.Heal e-learning modules on Oncogenomics include:

- Problem-Exercise, based on a realistic scenario relevant to the course's content , to activate the learning process and apply the gained competencies (starting point of the PBL cycle);
For each of the four Learning Objective (LO)
 - Teachers' tutorials (video lessons) presenting the main study topics of the learning unit;
 - Reading materials with useful inputs for the problem's solution (scientific papers, reports, references to legislation, etc.);
 - Supplementary materials to be used by participants for in-depth analysis and further research, including relevant bibliographic references and websites addresses;
- Problem solution, i.e. the proposed solutions to the problem (end point of the PBL cycle).

The evaluations tools of the course include:

- Self-assessment questionnaires, to fill in before and after each of the four LO modules.
- qualifying questionnaire, to fill in at the end of the course to earn CME credits
- Satisfaction questionnaire, to fill in at the end of the course to gather users' comments on the overall quality of the training programme

3.2 Dissemination

The Italian version of the Can.Heal e-learning course on Oncogenomics was available online on 15 February 2024 on the ISS training platform EDUISS (www.eduiss.it). The e-learning course can be accessed by registration on the platform and is free of charge. As of 30 September, 2,983 participants registered for the course. They were physicians (38%), biologists (44%) and pharmacists (17%). Overall, 1,322 (44%) completed the course and gained CME credits, 625 (21%) initiated the activities and were in the process of completing the course and 1036 (35%) did not yet started the course's activities. The leaflet of the Italian course (**Appendix 1**) was used to disseminate it to key associations and Can.Heal partners (ACC).

The English version of the Can.Heal e-learning course was available online on 15 September 2024 on the EDUISS e-learning platform (www.eduiss.it) in the section devoted to the international trainings (Laboratorium). The leaflet of the English course (**Appendix 2**) served as a dissemination resource to the Can.Heal partners (ACC). Adhesion strongly relies on the partners' relay in their country to reach relevant professional networks and associations. The course's dissemination started in Latvia, Belgium, Malta, Slovenia, Greece, Portugal. We asked the Consortium partners involved in WP13 to setup a dissemination plan in their country.

The Spanish version of the Can.Heal e-learning course went online on 30 September 2024 on the e-oncologia training platform (<https://e-oncologia.org/cursos/oncogenomica/>) of the Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO). Fifteen days later 325 participants had already enrolled (158 Physicians, 108 Biologists, 59 Pharmacists).

The e-learning courses can be accessed by registering on the platforms and are free of charge. Applicants must also give their consent for their pseudonymised data to be processed for research purposes. Courses are available until different dates depending on the launch date of each platform and the rules set by the national or international institution accrediting the course for continuing medical education (one year is the minimum period). The e-courses will be continued and updated through the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine.

3.3 Impact assessment

The design of the training material allows to assess the impact of the Can.Heal e-learning course on Oncogenomics by analyzing data collected during its deployment. More specifically the impact will be evaluated in terms of adhesion (number of participants in the different countries, number of completed courses, distribution by demographic and professional characteristics), effectiveness (knowledge increase pre-post test, score in the certification test) and users satisfaction (quality and utility of the content, usability of the platform, suggestions for improvement).

The same tools are used in all the countries involved in the pilot implementation of the Can.Heal e-learning course on Oncogenomics. This allows to gather comparable data at an unprecedented European scale. The impact assessment can be sorted by health professionals category, age, sex and country of origin to improve the interpretation of the results.

The methodology to assess the impact of the Can.Heal e-learning course leverages the work done for the assessment of the iPAAC e-learning course on Oncogenomics⁴. The latter was piloted in Italy, with English materials and with a limited number of participants. The results of the Can.Heal e-learning course will come from different pilots set up in different countries, which will provide a much larger basis for the statistical analyses from a European-wide perspective.

4. Conclusions and lessons learnt

4.1 Factors facilitating adhesion of the users

We developed an e-learning course focusing on the basic principles and applications of genomics in oncology. The course is aimed for professionals that are not specialised in genetics with the purpose of improving knowledge and knowhow of diverse groups of professional categories that do not normally deal with oncogenomics in their daily practice. For this reason a specific attention was paid to incentive factors that could increase the interest and facilitate the adhesion of the targeted professionals.

The most significant facilitating factors we considered were the following.

CME accreditation

The possibility to earn Continuing Medical Education credits is at the same time a quality assurance for the value of the educational initiative and an incentive to participate, particularly in countries where CME programs are mandatory. A major issue was the need for professionals to have the credits recognised by their local country-specific systems. We overcame this issue by obtaining accreditation by a European provider (EACCME, see section 2.5) who has signed agreements with most European countries to recognize European Credits. For the other countries, like Italy and Spain, we applied for local CME accreditation with the national authorities.

Cost-free access

The possibility to access the Can.Heal e-learning course cost-free is particularly valuable for participants. In general CME training does imply a fee, which might have a negative impact on registrations. For the Can.Heal training, the expenses needed to develop and deploy the course were budgeted in the frame of the project, allowing to propose it for free.

Use of native languages

A specific issue raised by participants in the iPAAC small pilot⁴, was the difficulty to learn complex matters, that are often not very close to the background education or professional experience, by studying in a language in which they are not fluent or proficient. Offering the course in a non-native language represents a limit, both in terms of efficacy of the training for those who decide to participate, and in terms of registration for those who are discouraged by the additional obstacle of the language and decide to drop out or not participate. The decision to translate the Can.Heal Oncogenomics course in Italian improved remarkably the number of attendees on the EDUISS platform (about 3,000 enrolled in 7 months compared to less than 500 in one year for the iPAAC previous version of the course).

Flexibility of the e-learning mode

The distance learning mode represents an advantage for the users, when the course is designed such as interactions with teacher is not required. Flexible and fully independent programs are well suited for the needs of Health Professionals, whatever their age or career stage.

4.2 Factors facilitating adoption

In the frame of Can.Heal we developed and piloted a distance training initiative in Oncogenomics that can be in principle adopted by other countries either as it is or as a model to develop similar courses.

We propose the following most significant factors for optimal implementation :

Use of existing national platforms

The delivery of the Can.Heal course strongly relied on existing facilities available for training health professionals who work for the National Health Service. Such platforms are in place in many countries in reference institutions or scientific associations. Their use increased during the COVID pandemic, when distance learning modalities rapidly became popular. The availability of training platforms that the professional are already familiar with contributes to increase the visibility and dissemination of the courses. From a logistic point of view there is also a clear advantage in including a course in an institutional context with a clear mission on training and using platforms that are already running. This contributes to make a course more cost-effective and sustainable in the long run.

E-learning mode

Adopting e-learning is cost-effective, flexible (more acceptable by the users) and easily replicable in different times and contexts, which considerably increase the impact of the course by aiming at a larger audience that could not have attended otherwise.

Technological solutions

The Can.Heal e-learning course was implemented in a technological environment that eased its export as a Moodle. This facilitated its adaptation to other languages and its implementation on platforms other than the original EDUISS, because Moodle is a common standard. The chosen technological solution is thus relevant for the replicability of the educational model and has an impact on the cost-effectiveness of the intervention as well. The use of AI-based tools, developed specifically for multilingual translations, proved to be quite effective in reducing time and costs for the adaptation to different languages. However, it was also evident that AI alone is not sufficient. Revision of the texts by experts in the field was essential to achieve accurate and faithful translations, both in terms of syntax and semantics.

Performance indicators

The Can.Heal e-learning course incorporates assessment tools allowing performance indicators for either a training purpose (self-assessment of participants at different steps of the course) or for assessing the impact of the course (final assessment for CME certification and satisfaction questionnaire). For potential future adopters of the intervention, providing 'by design' performance indicators is an added value and a key element to be accounted for cost-effectiveness assessment.

4.3 Challenges

Intellectual property rights (IPR)

The dissemination of the Can.Heal Oncogenomics course on different platforms and within different countries implies IPR issues related to: i) the training material (the material was developed by a team of medical geneticists and e-learning experts appointed by ISS) in English and Italian; ii) the translations in other languages (translated material underwent proof reading by experts appointed by the Consortium partners and these experts were responsible for the correct translation of the original materials); iii) the e-learning platform (it was set up by the ISS-Training Service following the PBL methodology that requires a definite sequence of the proposed activities. Adaptations of the platform in each country should faithfully reproduce the PBL method and fairly recognize the role of ISS who developed and shared the training material).

All these elements were covered in a letter of intent, which the template is shown in Appendix 3, to be signed by ISS and each counterpart implementing the course within the Consortium.

Adaptation to language barriers

The delivery of the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics strongly relies for CME credits on the national platforms with which local Health Professionals are familiar. These organizations are not always available in European countries. In these cases a viable solution is to redirect the professionals to the English version of the course on the EDUISS platform, e.g. to support the delivery in a country by using the English version to maximise accessibility. This could be a sub-optimal solution for countries where using the native language would be more effective for participants.

Furthermore, delivery of the course in a native language requires a team of experts to review the translated texts with artificial intelligence-based technologies. The quality of machine translations is highly dependent on the size of the population and more effort may be required for more rarely spoken languages.

Sustainability

An important element to consider for long-term sustainability is the need to periodically update scientific material. A course that covers the fundamentals and main applications of oncogenomics, given the rapidly changing landscape of the field, may need to be revised every 3-5 years.

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Table 2. Learning Objectives (LOs). Description of LOs contents and the corresponding core competencies used to develop the learning materials.

Learning Objectives (LOs)	Contents description	LO-related core competencies of physicians
<p>1. To describe the basic elements of human genetics and oncogenetics and the OMICS technologies used to identify the molecular signatures of cancer</p>	<p>Fundamental principles of human genetics, with a focus on oncogenetics (<i>i.e.</i>, somatically acquired or germline-transmitted changes). Basic information on currently available OMICS technologies to identify molecular cancer signatures.</p>	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic knowledge of genetics within own field of clinical practice • Knowledge of the concept of somatic genetic changes • Knowledge of the role of genomic changes in the pathophysiology and treatment of cancer • Understanding the hereditary predisposition to cancer, including the polygenic and multifactorial nature of cancer risk • Knowledge of the major hereditary cancer syndromes • Understanding the specific characteristics of hereditary cancer syndromes that may distinguish them from sporadic cancers • Understanding the differences between hereditary and non-hereditary cancer
<p>2. To describe the currently available genetic/genomic tests for cancer screening and diagnosis, and their applications</p> <p>3. To define the role of genetic testing and counselling in the risk assessment of hereditary cancers</p>	<p>Information on the existing genetic and genomic tests to be used for cancer screening and diagnosis, with an emphasis on the importance of genetic counselling, data interpretation, and incidental findings.</p> <p>Information on the role of genetic testing in assessing the possible occurrence of germline variants in cancer susceptibility genes and in estimating the risk to develop cancer based on personal and family history.</p>	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of how genomic testing can be used to guide therapy and dose selection in cancer patients • Knowledge of the availability of screening tests and procedures for those identified as having higher lifetime cancer risk • Understanding genetic testing types and result interpretation • Awareness of incidental and secondary findings from somatic tumour profiling • Defining the general characteristic of tumour spectrum of known syndromes • Awareness of overlapping phenotypes for the common syndromes that generate differential diagnosis for hereditary syndromes based on presenting cancer • Knowing the interpretation and the importance of family history in assessing disease predisposition • Understanding the importance of family history as a risk factor, regardless of gene testing <p>Attitudes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acknowledging the impact of genetic information on patients and their family • Recognizing the need for consents to disclose a particular diagnosis to relatives • Recognizing the importance of multidisciplinary work and the role of genetic counsellors as well as mental health professionals to assist patients as they process difficult information
<p>4. To identify the main applications of pharmacogenomics and personalized medicine in oncology</p>	<p>Basic elements of the role and range of applications of pharmacogenomics and personalized medicine in oncology.</p>	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the role of genomic changes in the pathophysiology and treatment of cancer • Knowledge on how genomic testing can be used to guide therapy and dose selection in patients with cancer • Awareness of risk-reducing measures in high-risk patients and relatives, including chemoprevention and prophylactic surge

Table 2. List of the training materials developed in the Can.Heal e-learning “Oncogenomics for Health Professionals”. Description of the materials developed in each PBL cycle step and corresponding Learning Objective (LO).

PBL cycle step	Item	Description	Materials
Problem	Problem presentation	Video tutorial	.pptx and video tutorial
Exploration phase	LO1 Basic principles of human genetics	Self-assessment (pre-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
		Video tutorial	.pptx and video tutorial
		Reading materials for individual study	Document (22 pages)
		Self-assessment (post-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
	LO2 Genetic and Genomic tests in oncology	Self-assessment (pre-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
		Video tutorial	.pptx and video tutorial
		Reading materials for individual study	Document (17 pages)
		Self-assessment (post-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
	LO3 Genetic Counselling in oncology	Self-assessment (pre-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
		Video tutorial	.pptx and video tutorial
		Reading materials for individual study	Document (22 pages)
		Self-assessment (post-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
	LO4 Pharmacogenomics in oncology	Self-assessment (pre-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
		Video tutorial	.pptx and video tutorial
		Reading materials for individual study	Document (16 pages)
		Self-assessment (post-test)	Questionnaire 12 MCQ
	LO1-LO4	Supporting materials	Docx file with key-words, relevant bibliography and sitography
Problem	Problem solution	Video tutorial	.pptx and video tutorial
CME credits	Certification test	Final certificative test to be passed (at least 75% correct answers) to get CME credits	Questionnaire 60 MCQ (15 per each LO)
User Satisfaction	Satisfaction test	Questions addressing different dimensions: overall quality, quality of the resources offered, technical support, platform functioning	Questionnaire 18 Likert type questions + open questions for free comments

Appendixes

List of documents reported as Appendix

Appendix 1

Leaflet to disseminate the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics to Italian health professionals on the EDUISS training platform.

Appendix 2

Leaflet to disseminate the English version of the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics to non-italian health professionals on the EDUISS training platform.

Appendix 3

Draft letter of intent to disseminate the translated versions of the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics on training platforms other than EDUISS.

Appendix 1

Leaflet to disseminate the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics to Italian health professionals on the EDUISS training platform.

FACULTY

Paola GHIORZO, University of Genoa and IRCCS Policlinico Hospital San Martino, Genoa, Italy

Maurizio GENUARDI, Institute of Genomic Medicine, Faculty of Medicine "A. Gemelli", Catholic University of Sacred Heart, Rome, Italy

Emilio DI MARIA, Department of Health Sciences, University of Genoa and University Unit of Medical Genetics, Galliera Hospital, Genoa, Italy

CME CREDITS AND REGISTRATION

A total of 12 hours is allocated to the course. The course was accredited by the European Accreditation Council for Continuing Medical Education (EACCME). Registration is free of charge and can be done via the ISS portal for distance learning <https://www.eduiss.it> at the following link: <https://www.eduiss.it/course/index.php?categoryid=78>

ORGANISED BY

ITALIAN NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF HEALTH (ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITÀ, ISS), ROME, IT

Distance Learning Course

ONCOGENOMICS FOR HEALTH PROFESSIONALS

Open until 9 April 2025

E-learning course on the basic principles of oncogenomics for physicians (all specialties), biologists and pharmacists. The course was developed within the CAN.HEAL (*Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics platform*) project, funded by the European Commission (www.canheal.eu). The overall aim of CAN.HEAL is to integrate cancer diagnosis, treatment and prevention interventions that make use of genomic information and to promote their coordinated adoption in Europe. To this end, updating the knowledge base of healthcare professionals is of crucial importance.

TRAINING OBJECTIVES AND TEACHING METHOD

The course aims to improve the knowledge and attitude of healthcare professionals regarding the basic principles of genetics and the main clinical applications of genomic technologies in cancer prevention and treatment. The training objectives were identified through a systematic literature review and a Delphi consensus by an international panel of experts. The teaching methodology is inspired by the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach. The training course alternates video tutorials by the lecturers, questionnaires and background materials.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix 2

Leaflet to disseminate the English version of the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics to non-italian health professionals on the EDUISS training platform.

FACULTY

Paola GHIORZO, University of Genoa and IRCCS Policlinico Hospital San Martino, Genoa, Italy

Maurizio GENUARDI, Institute of Genomic Medicine, Faculty of Medicine "A. Gemelli", Catholic University of Sacred Heart, Rome, Italy

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Appendix 3

Draft letter of intent to disseminate the translated versions of the Can.Heal course on Oncogenomics on training platforms other than EDUISS.

Letter of Intent

This Letter of Intent is to express the willingness of the [redacted] Institute (acronym, city, country) to implement, on its institutional e-learning platform, the basic course "Oncogenomics for Health Professionals" developed by the Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS, Rome, Italy) in the framework of the CAN.HEAL European project (www.canheal.eu). The development and dissemination of this distance course in Europe is part of the objectives of Work Package 13 on Education and Training.

For the realisation of the above-mentioned purpose:

1) ISS undertakes to provide [redacted] with the original course contents developed in English, their translation into French/Spanish/[redacted] obtained with the DEEP-L software for automated translation and the Moodle version of the application used to deliver the e-learning course through the EDUISS platform at ISS;

2) [redacted] undertakes to:

- check the automated translation and improve the French/Spanish/[redacted] translation to make it faithful to the original content;
- give visibility within the course to ISS intellectual property by affixing the ISS logo and appropriate explanatory disclaimers;
- make it explicit within the various teaching units that the teachers developed the original materials in English and that [redacted] took charge of their translation into French/Spanish/[redacted].
- not modify the teaching methodology of the course in any way, and stick faithfully to the original layout of the file (-.story) with which the course is delivered on the EDUISS platform.

The parties are informed that the events promoted by ISS are subject to a Quality System, therefore they ensure their adherence, in order to guarantee the conformity of the event to the expected quality standards.

ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA'
Training Service
Dr. Alfonso Mazzaccara

INSTITUTE [redacted]
Full affiliation
Name and Surname

Date:

THE ISS ADOPTS A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR TRAINING PROCESSES CERTIFIED BY DNV ISO 9001

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